

Database:

Embase Classic+Embase <1947 to 2021 December 14>

#	Query	Results from 14 Dec 2021
1	laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/	27,743
2	exp discectomy/ or diskectom*.mp. or discectom*.mp.	15,532
3	exp decompression surgery/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.	63,084
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/	39,189
5	exp Spinal Disease/su	52,390
6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	150,681
7	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	324,884
8	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp.	5,889
9	orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/	187,659
10	exp orthopedic surgery/	569,905
11	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	51,869
12	(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	107,646
13	radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/	55,269
14	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Disease/	297,647
15	spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	383,024
16	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebra/	31,992

17	12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	608,373
18	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	98,317
19	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	71,387
20	telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or (mobile adj3 phone*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	143,052
21	(smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	27,363
22	tablet*.mp. or exp Tablet/	119,188
23	(mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Application/	20,769
24	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	2,218
25	telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/	481
26	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade	9,374

	name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
27	((health adj3 communicat*) or (medic* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp medical information/	165,276
28	(medical adj3 informatic*).mp. or exp medical informatics/ or (informat* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	28,755
29	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp.	638
30	((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)).mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	14,476
31	((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp interpersonal communication/)	1,027
32	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp home visit/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	17,911
33	(real-time adj3 support*).mp.	1,220
34	((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,990,706
35	((followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device	39,058

	trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
36	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	3,925
37	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	7,492
38	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	13
39	simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	551,048
40	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	2,013
41	exp analgesia/ or analgesia*.mp. or (pain adj3 manag*).mp.	253,338
42	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	530
43	(patient* adj3 educat*).mp. or exp patient education/ or (client* adj3 educat*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade	160,159

	name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
44	(patient* adj3 car*).mp. or exp patient care/ or (car* adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,646,182
45	(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	112,123
46	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	151,832
47	((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	16,854
48	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	39,104
49	recover*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,011,967
50	convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	746,515

51	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,498
52	(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/	9,520
53	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or ((preoperative adj3 exercise*) or (pre-operative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	3,916
54	((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (adaptive adj3 behavior*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*)).mp. or exp psychological adjustment/ or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*).mp. or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or exp physiological adaptation/ or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	82,608
55	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,492
56	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword	6,953

	heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	
57	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	17,956
58	discharg*.mp. or exp hospital discharge/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	561,427
59	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or post-discharg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	24,218
60	(transition* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	1,970
61	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]	268,406
62	7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	950,018
63	17 and 62	142,850
64	6 or 18 or 63	236,409
65	55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61	792,809
66	19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54	6,231,751
67	64 and 65 and 66	8,770

68	limit 67 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	8,451
69	limit 68 to (article or article in press or books or chapter or conference paper or "conference review" or editorial or erratum or letter or note or "review" or short survey or tombstone)	6,061